

Digitalizing the Medical Records of Patients: Medical History for Doctors, and Patients

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Abstract:

Each time when we visit new hospital or clinic, we are asked about our problems, and its history. In this paper, we have discussed about digitalizing the medical records of any patients, for conveniency of Patients as well as doctors, based on study of their previous medical records as medical history.

Introduction:

We shall begin with registration of a patient to be admitted for treatment with following examples in pictures.

In the following two pictures, medical records of author are provided for vaccine against Covid-19. The first picture has registration number 11826200, with a QR code provided which further shows about citizenship number.

When medical records of any person is included, as per date wise basis, then some links by means of Internet, can be provided, which would provided entire medical records of any person, whenever needed, for treatment.

Discussion:

All of the medical records are needed to be digitalized by hospitals and clinics, so that medical history of examination for certain illness can be cured properly. That would mean, any person can do treatment whenever he would like, and doctors would have conveniency to provide treatment, by observing entire previous history of that particular illness, or even other illness in generality, depending upon the medical history.

In Nepal:

In Nepal, Ministry of Health and Population, Nepal Health Research Council, Nepal Medical Council and such bodies can be found, which works in the Health care services. It would need laws, policies and implementation, so that, each time when we visit hospital or clinic, we wouldn't have to carry our medical records book with examination of doctors, or to be examined. Our medical records would be at our hands, where as a permanent archive as per governing body would provide our each and every medical record for our treatment on generalised as well as specific basis, based on our illness.

खोप लगाउन इच्छुक व्यक्तिको विवरण कार्ड

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Problems that might arise is due to transparency in medical records, as all peoples wouldn't prefer their medical history records to be publicly available in archives of web pages, to be studied by doctors, and last treatment provided would be more emphasized by doctors for the treatment of patients.

Conclusion:

Thus, by means of registration number, which can be further reduced to citizenship number or any national means of identification of peoples, our medical history can be permanently archived, that would show, entire of our medical history. That would mean, our medical record book, would be in our hands, where as digitalized medical records would be available in Internet, to be accessed by individual peoples as well as health professionals. Like as mass, length and time, defined in S.I. units, as per their means, our health too is determined by similar factors, by means of generalized study, as per our functioning of body, and providing medical history of patients would not only be fruitful for doctors, but also to patients, to know and understand about functioning of our body.